

ISic0862

I.Sicily inscription 0862

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

sarcophagus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Βουλκακία

2. Τερεντία

3. εύσεβής

4. και αγαθή

5. ἔζησεν ἔτη

6. · μ ·

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644911

PHI 140339

Bibliography

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